

HISTORY OF ENGLISH CULTURE

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Annotation: The way of life of England is from time to time sensitive to split effortlessly from the way of life of the United Kingdom, so influential has English way of life been at the societies of the British Islands and, on the opposite hand, given the quantity to which different societies have informed lifestyles in England. This article is about the history and evolution of the English culture.

Key words: History, culture of English, language, tradition, nation.

It was observed by that remarkable twelfth-century chronicler Henry of Huntington that an interest in the past was one of the distinguishing characteristics of humans as compared with the other animals. The medium by which speakers of a language communicate their thoughts and feelings to others, the tool with which they conduct their business or the government of millions of people, the vehicle by which has been transmitted the science, the philosophy, the poetry of the culture is surely worthy of study. It is not to be expected that everyone should be a philologist or should master the technicalities of linguistic science. But it is reasonable to assume that a liberally educated person should know something of the structure of his or her language, its position in the world and its relation to other tongues, the wealth of its vocabulary together with the sources from which that vocabulary has been and is being enriched, and the complex relationships among the many different varieties of speech that are gathered under the single name of the English language. The diversity of cultures that find expression in it is a reminder that the history of English is a story of cultures in contact during the past 1,500 years. If we say that political, economic and social forces affect the language. These forces shape language in every way,

above all in the number and distribution of speakers and the so-called "sociology of language", but also in the meaning of words, dialects of the spoken language, and even in structures. from grammar. The history of this or that language is closely related to the history of the peoples who speak this language. Therefore, the purpose of this book is to treat the history of the English language not only for the professional student, but also as a cultural subject in the opinion of all educated people in an interesting way, while making sufficient references to the technical issues related to the scientific principles of language development.

British culture is influenced by the history of the united nations, including its traditionally Christian religious life, its relationships with other European cultures, the traditions of England, Wales, Scotland, and Ireland, as well as the legacy of the British Empire. Although British culture is a distinct entity, the cultures of England, Scotland, Wales, and Northern Ireland are all distinctive and have varying degrees of overlap. There is a high regard for British literature. Playwrights, poets, and authors from Britain are among the most well-known artists in the world. There the modern book was created. Britain has also made important contributions to television, painting, music, film, and other creative endeavors. In addition, the Church of England, the mother church of the Anglican Communion, the third-largest Christian denomination, is headquartered in the UK. In addition to having some of the oldest colleges in the world, Britain has made significant contributions to philosophy, science, technology, and medicine. It is also home to a number of well-known inventors and scientists. Beginning in the UK, the Industrial Revolution had a significant impact on global family, socioeconomic, and cultural situations. Significant British influence can be seen as a result of the British Empire in the language, laws, cultures, and institutions of its former colonies, the majority of which are now Commonwealth of Nations members. These nations, which make up the Anglosphere, are some of Great Britain's closest allies. British culture, notably British cuisine, was impacted by British colonies and dominions. The British place

a high value on sports, and several sports including rugby, football, and cricket have their roots there.

The United Kingdom has been called a "culture superpower". Additionally, London has been referred to as a global cultural hub. In 2013 and 2014, the UK was placed third in the world (after Germany and Canada) in a worldwide opinion survey conducted for the BBC.

History Historically, the British Isles were a culturally homogeneous nation with developed national traditions; however, as the British Empire grew, the nation absorbed other races from throughout the world.

Since the end of World War II, British culture has highlighted the contributions that South Asians, Afro-Caribbeans, and other immigrants have made to diversity.

Language

The British Library is home to the heroic poem Beowulf in Old English.

English, which was first spoken in early medieval England, is the only language spoken by an estimated 95% of Britons. The UK's official language is de facto English.

The other seven languages recognized by the British government under the European Charter for Regional or Minority Languages are Welsh, Scottish Gaelic, Scots, Cornish, Irish, Ulster Scots, and British Sign Language. Welsh Language Act of 1993 and Government of Wales Act of 1998 mandate that all students in state schools must either be taught in Welsh or study it as a second language until the age of sixteen. They also state that the Welsh and English languages should be treated equally in the public sector, to the extent that is reasonable and practicable. In Northern Ireland, Irish and Ulster Scots are only occasionally used in addition to English, usually in translations that were funded by the government. The Gaelic Language (Scotland) Act, passed by the Scottish Parliament in 2005, established Gaelic as an official language of Scotland and required the creation of a national strategy to guide the language's development. The Cornish language was extinct as

a primary language in Cornwall by the late 18th century, although it has since been restored.

Geographic accents

Between the four nations that make up There are notable regional accent and dialect distinctions throughout the UK as well as within each of them. In part, this can be attributed to the long history of immigration to the UK; for instance, several phrases used in Northern English dialects have Old Norse roots. Scottish, Welsh, and Hiberno-Irish dialects of the English language are unique from Standard English as well as the respective countries' native languages. The accent of Standard English in England and Wales is Received Pronunciation, but Scottish Standard English is a distinctive dialect specific to Scotland. Despite the high social status of these accents, there has been a change in schooling since the 1960s that favors more acceptance of regional English varieties. Close-by locations frequently have quite distinct dialects and accents, highlighting the huge variation of British accents. For instance, despite the fact that Liverpool and Manchester are only 35 miles (56 km) away, Scouse and Mancunian culture differ significantly. English dialect is widely employed in literature; for example, *Wuthering Heights* by Emily Bronte uses Yorkshire dialect.

References:

1. Braber, Natalie. "Why does the UK have so many accents?". *The Conversation*. Retrieved 15 June 2019.
2. Calder, Simon (22 December 2007). "London, capital of the world". *The Independent*. London.
3. E. J. Kirchner and J. Sperling, *Global Security Governance: Competing Perceptions of Security in the 21st Century* (London: Taylor & Francis, 2007), p. 100.
4. McArthur, Tom (2002), *The Oxford Guide to World English*, Oxford University Press, p. 43.
5. Dushatova, S. (2022). EVFEMIZM TUSHUNCHASI TAHLILI.

6. Dushatova, S., & Davronova, X. (2023). NUTQNI ENG KICHIK MA'NO ANGLATUVCHI BIRLIKLARGA AJRATISH. *YOUTH, SCIENCE, EDUCATION: TOPICAL ISSUES, ACHIEVEMENTS AND INNOVATIONS*, 2(8), 97-103.
7. Dushatova, S., & Azimova, H. (2023). ONA TILINI IKKINCHI TIL O'RGANISHDAGI AHAMIYATI. *YOUTH, SCIENCE, EDUCATION: TOPICAL ISSUES, ACHIEVEMENTS AND INNOVATIONS*, 2(8), 104-108.
8. qizi Dushatova, S. B., & G'ulomjon qizi Esajonova, F. (2023, January). METHODS OF HISTORY TEACHING AND THEIR CLASSIFICATION. In *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE" THE TIME OF SCIENTIFIC PROGRESS"* (Vol. 2, No. 5, pp. 161-169).
9. qizi Dushatova, S. B., & qizi Qodiraliyeva, N. I. (2022). EFFECTIVE METHODS OF LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES. *International Academic Research Journal Impact Factor 7.4*, 1(5), 63-67.
10. qizi Dushatova, S. B., & Shahnoza, T. (2023, January). TIL VA NUTQDAGI LAKUNA: MADANIYATLARARO VA MATN ASPEKTLARI. In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: PROBLEMS AND SCIENTIFIC SOLUTIONS*. (Vol. 2, No. 8, pp. 34-37).
11. qizi Dushatova, S. B., & qizi Qo'chqorova, S. X. (2023, January). TIL O'QITISHDA O'YIN METODIDAN FOYDALANISH. In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: PROBLEMS AND SCIENTIFIC SOLUTIONS*. (Vol. 2, No. 8, pp. 27-33).
12. qizi Dushatova, S. B., & qizi Muxtorova, D. A. (2023). BOLALARGA XORIJIY TIL O'RGATISH METODIKASI. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT IN THE GLOBAL SCIENCE*, 2(9), 140-145.
13. qizi Dushatova, S. B., & Rahmatullayeva, Z. (2023, January). BOLALARNING RIVOJLANISHIDA ONA TILINING AHAMIYATI. In *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE" THE TIME OF SCIENTIFIC PROGRESS"* (Vol. 2, No. 5, pp. 154-160).

14. qizi Dushatova, S. B. (2023, January). TINISH BELGILARINING YOZMA NUTQDAGI AHAMIYATI. In *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE "THE TIME OF SCIENTIFIC PROGRESS"* (Vol. 2, No. 5, pp. 170-174).
15. Qobilova, M., & Abdullayeva, D. (2022, November). THE ROLE OF ABDULLAH AVLONI IN EDUCATION. In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES* (Vol. 1, No. 2, pp. 117-119).
16. Umaraliyevna, K. M. The History of Word Borrowing Process in the Uzbek and English Languages. *JournalNX*, 105-107.
17. Kosimova, M. U. (2022). THE DEVELOPMENT PROCESS OF THE SUBJECT OF STYLISTICS AND ITS MAIN TASKS. *CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES*, 3(11), 1-7.
18. Kosimova, M. U. (2022). Different classification of functional styles. *Ученый XXI века*, (4 (85)), 7-9.
19. SHOFIYEV, O. B. (2021). CHINGIZ AYTMATOV AND UZBEK LITERATURE. *THEORETICAL & APPLIED SCIENCE Учредители: Теоретическая и прикладная наука*, (12), 1170-1173.
20. Shodiyeva, G., & Ismatova, S. (2022). O'ZBEK TILSHUNOSLIGIDA SO'Z TURKUMLARI MASALASI. *Eurasian Journal of Academic Research*, 2(7), 103-105.
21. Gafurov, B. Z. (2020). ANALYSIS OF THE RELATIONSHIP OF MEDICAL TERMINOLOGY WITH SEGMENT PHONOSTYLISTICS OF THE NOUN IN RUSSIAN, UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (1), 464-466.